

Robot-assisted Procedure for Pedicle Screw Fixation

1st Clemente Lauretti

Unit of Advanced Robotics and human-centred technologies
Università Campus Bio-Medico
 Rome, Italy
 c.lauretti@unicampus.it

2nd Francesca Cordella

Unit of Advanced Robotics and human-centred technologies
Università Campus Bio-Medico
 Rome, Italy
 f.cordella@unicampus.it

3rd Christian Tamantini

Unit of Advanced Robotics and human-centred technologies
Università Campus Bio-Medico
 Rome, Italy
 c.tamantini@unicampus.it

4th Cosimo Gentile

Unit of Advanced Robotics and human-centred technologies
Università Campus Bio-Medico
 Rome, Italy
 c.gentile@unicampus.it

5th Francesco Scotto Di Luzio

Unit of Advanced Robotics and human-centred technologies
Università Campus Bio-Medico
 Rome, Italy
 f.scottodiluzio@unicampus.it

6th Loredana Zollo

Unit of Advanced Robotics and human-centred technologies
Università Campus Bio-Medico
 Rome, Italy
 l.zollo@unicampus.it

Abstract—The objective of this paper is to propose a new approach to robot-aided pedicle screw fixation based on a Surgeon-Robot Shared control that makes the tapping procedure, i.e. threading the patient’s pedicle, semi-autonomous. The surgeon has a full control over the surgical intervention that appears more comfortable and less tiring. Tests, aimed at assessing surgeon postures during the procedure, were carried out on eight subjects performing the tapping operation onto a spine phantom.

Index Terms—Human-Centered Robotics; Physically Assistive Devices; Medical Robots and Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

PEDICLE screw fixation has become the standard procedure in clinical practice to stabilize the thoracic or lumbar spine in patients with spinal instability or deformity [1].

Due to the anatomical proximity of the vertebral pedicles to a number of significant tissues (e.g., spinal cord, nerve root and blood vessels), accurate screw placement is essential to avoid neurological, vascular, and visceral injuries for the patient [2].

The tapping procedure, differently from the drilling one, consists of threading the patient’s pedicle for a more accurate screw insertion. Due to the accuracy needed in performing this operation, it is fundamental for the surgeon to accurately control the torque exerted by the surgical tool onto the patient. This may lead to increased geometric accuracy and can thus have an impact on the patient’s safety.

The aim of this paper is to propose a novel approach to robot-aided pedicle screw fixation that, based on a Surgeon-Robot Shared Control, makes the tapping procedure semi-autonomous. It allows the surgeon to i) accurately move the

robot end-effector, i.e. the surgical tapper, by means of a hands-on approach along a pre-planned axis, ii) continuously manage the forces exerted onto the patient spine during the tapping phase and iii) modulate the torque about the tapping axis by adequately tuning the tool-bone interaction force along the same axis.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. The proposed Surgeon-Robot Shared Control for semi-autonomous tapping

The proposed Surgeon-Robot Shared control can be derived from a conventional Inverse Dynamic Control described by the following equation

$$\tau_c = \hat{\mathbf{B}}(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{F}_v\dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{F}_s \text{sign}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{q}) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{q})$ is the robot inertia matrix, $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})$ accounts for Centrifugal and Coriolis effects, \mathbf{F}_v is the viscous friction torque, $\mathbf{F}_s \text{sign}(\dot{\mathbf{q}})$ is the static friction torque, $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{q})$ is the gravity contribution, \mathbf{q} , $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\ddot{\mathbf{q}}$ are the robot joint position, angular velocity and acceleration, respectively, and τ is the torque supplied by the actuators and \mathbf{y} is the modified control law.

In particular, the conventional control law \mathbf{y} [3] was re-designed as follows [4],

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger(\mathbf{q})[\ddot{\mathbf{x}}_d - \dot{\mathbf{J}}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{A}d_1^{-1}(\mathbf{K}_D\mathbf{A}d_1\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}} + \mathbf{K}_P\mathbf{A}d_1\tilde{\mathbf{x}} + \mathbf{K}_F\mathbf{X}_F)] \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{J}^\dagger is the right pseudo-inverse of the robot geometric Jacobian and $\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}} = [\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{p}}}; \dot{\tilde{\varphi}}]$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{x}} = [\tilde{\mathbf{p}}; \tilde{\varphi}]$ are the velocity and position errors expressed in the base reference frame $[\mathbf{X}_B, \mathbf{Y}_B, \mathbf{Z}_B]$, respectively (see Fig. 1). Vectors $\tilde{\mathbf{p}}$ and $\tilde{\varphi}$

This paper was supported partly by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (PON Project research and innovation 2014-2020) with the ARONA project (CUP: B26G18000390005) and partly by the Campus Bio-Medico University Strategic Projects (Call 2018) with the SAFE-MOVER project

Fig. 1. Surgeon-robot configuration and reference frames for the proposed semi-autonomous tapping procedure

are the Cartesian position and velocity error, respectively. Conversely, $\tilde{\varphi}$ is the angular position and $\dot{\tilde{\varphi}}$ is the velocity error. In order to meet task specifications for the tapping procedure, the robot reference motion should be purposely planned by means of image-based navigation systems that, depending on the target bone, find the desired direction for the tapping axis. Ad_1 in (2) is an adjoint matrix that was purposely added in order to transform the velocity error $\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}}$ and position error $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ from the base frame $[\mathbf{X}_B, \mathbf{Y}_B, \mathbf{Z}_B]$ to the end-effector frame $[\mathbf{X}_{ee}, \mathbf{Y}_{ee}, \mathbf{Z}_{ee}]$ and is expressed as

$$\text{Ad}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{ee}^B & \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{ee} \mathbf{R}_{ee}^B \\ \mathbf{O}_{(3 \times 3)} & \mathbf{R}_{ee}^B \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (3)$$

\mathbf{R}_{ee}^B is the rotation matrix that expresses the orientation of the end-effector frame with respect to the base frame and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{ee}$ is the skew-symmetric matrix of the end-effector Cartesian position \mathbf{p}_{ee} .

B. Experimental validation

The proposed Surgeon-Robot shared control was tested on eight subjects. They were asked to tap the pedicle screw path in the dummy spine in three different modalities: i) Traditional Manual Tapping (TMT), ii) Traditional Robot-aided Tapping (TRT), iii) Innovative Robot-aided Tapping (IRT) (see [4] for more details about modalities description).

The overall setup used to validate the proposed approach consists of the following components:

- KUKA Light Weight Robot 4+: It is a 7 DoFs robotic arm with position and torque sensors at joints. The communication between the Kuka controller and a remote PC is guaranteed by the Robot Operating System (ROS) via a UDP communication protocol with a frequency of 500 Hz
- BTS SMART-D Motion Capture System: It is composed of 8 optoelectronic cameras with an acquisition rate of

60 Hz and an accuracy less than 0.1mm over a 2×2 m area

- Surgical tool: it taps pedicle to prepare for screw placement.
- Anthropomorphic spine phantom: it is a lumbar spine, L1 to sacrum, produced by Sawbones, made of solid foam.

The Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) scale [5] was adopted to evaluate the subjects' exposure to ergonomic risk factors associated with upper extremity Musculo-Skeletal Disorders (MSDs). Using the RULA guidelines, a single score, ranging from 1 (negligible risk exposure to MSDs) to 7 (high risk exposure to MSDs) was generated thanks to the RULA worksheet shown in [5].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The experimental results of the force control action demonstrate that the proposed control is highly reactive and accurate; indeed the measured normal force, i.e. the force supplied by the user along the tapping axis (opportunistically scaled), is well-tracked by the torque exerted by the tapping tool (accuracy less than 3 Nm).

The mean value and standard deviation of the RULA scores obtained by the subjects during the TMT is 4.55 ± 1.26 , during the TRT is 3.47 ± 0.65 and during the IRT is 2.84 ± 0.36 . From these values it is evident that, during the TMT, the subjects assumed incorrect and uncomfortable postures, suggesting that for this mode there is a medium risk to incur in MSDs and some ergonomic improvements are required. The introduction of the robotic system that acts as positioning device (TRT modality) in this surgical procedure have a positive influence on the surgeon's postures, suggesting that for this mode there is a low risk to incur in MSDs and some ergonomic improvements may be needed. The users performing the surgical procedure in the IRT modality are not exposed to unsafe or incorrect posture, suggesting that there is a negligible risk to incur in MSDs and ergonomic improvements are not required.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The comparative analysis among the three tapping modalities in terms of subject's posture showed better results for the proposed approach with respect to the other methods.

Future works will be devoted to test the proposed approach in real settings first on cadavers and then on patients and to integrate a vision-based navigation system in the control loop.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Boos and J. Webb, "Pedicle screw fixation in spinal disorders: a european view," *European Spine Journal*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 2–18, 1997.
- [2] S.-I. Suk, W.-J. Kim, S.-M. Lee, J.-H. Kim, and E.-R. Chung, "Thoracic pedicle screw fixation in spinal deformities: are they really safe?" *Spine*, vol. 26, no. 18, pp. 2049–2057, 2001.
- [3] B. Siciliano and O. Khatib, *Springer handbook of robotics*. Springer, 2016.
- [4] C. Lauretti, F. Cordella, C. Tamantini, C. Gentile, F. S. di Luzio, and L. Zollo, "A surgeon-robot shared control for ergonomic pedicle screw fixation," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 2554–2561, 2020.
- [5] L. McAtamney and E. N. Corlett, "Rula: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders," *Applied ergonomics*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 91–99, 1993.